

An investigation into the contribution of institutional cultural paradigms to the effectiveness of postgraduate programmes: A comparative study of University of Moratuwa and University of Kelaniya

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Citation:

Subasinghe, R., & Wickramasinghe, V. (2010). An investigation into the contribution of institutional cultural paradigms to the effectiveness of postgraduate programmes: A comparative study of University of Moratuwa and University of Kelaniya. Proceedings of International Conference on Business and Information, Faculty of Commerce and Management Studies, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka, June 4, 13

This Version is available at: <http://www.kln.ac.lk/uokr/ICBI2010/11.pdf>

**AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE CONTRIBUTION OF
INSTITUTIONAL CULTURAL PARADIGMS TO THE
EFFECTIVENESS OF POSTGRADUATE PROGRAMS: A
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF UNIVERSITY OF MORATUWA
AND UNIVERSITY OF KELANIYA**

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ABSTRACT

Although the state university system of Sri Lanka requires undergraduate degree programmes to be provided free of charge, postgraduate degree programmes and other services such as consultancy and research and development can be provided on income generating basis. Nevertheless, evidence suggests that the state university system is not operating up to its potential in providing commercially viable postgraduate programmes on profit making basis.

This research questions whether the institutional cultural paradigms prevailing within the state university system impedes it from achieving strategic organizational objectives of survival, self-sustainability and growth. The study investigates and compares institutional cultural paradigms and effectiveness of postgraduate programmes of University of Moratuwa and University of Kelaniya, and investigates whether a particular paradigm is conducive for achieving strategic objectives than other cultural paradigms.

For the study, a random sample of 100 senior academic and administrative staff responsible for postgraduate programmes of Faculty of Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology of University of Moratuwa, and a random sample of 100 senior academic and administrative staff responsible for postgraduate programmes of Faculty of Science, Commerce and Management, Social Sciences, Humanities, Post Graduate Institute of Pali and Buddhist Studies, and Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology of University of Kelaniya responded. The institutional culture was measured based on the dimensions proposed by Denison and Mishra (1995) that consist of four dimensions, namely Consistency, Adaptability, Involvement and Mission. The effectiveness of postgraduate programmes were measured based on the dimensions proposed by Cameron (1978) that consists of four dimensions, namely, Academic (Academic Development of students, Professional Development of

Lecturers, Ability to acquire source), Morale, Adaptation to the External Environment and Field outside Programme.

It was found that University of Moratuwa has more conducive institutional culture compared to University of Kelaniya, although certain Faculties of University of Kelaniya have scored higher in some institutional cultural dimensions compared to the Faculties of University of Moratuwa. A similar trend was observed in aspect of the effectiveness of postgraduate programmes as well.

The research shows that healthy cultures lead to better effectiveness and technology oriented universities have comparatively conducive cultures that lead to greater effectiveness. This research will lay the foundation for future research into other factors influencing effectiveness and dynamics of existing cultural paradigms.

Key Words : Institutional Cultural Paradigms, Organizational Culture, Post Graduate Programmes, Effectiveness

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Since the early 1980, a wave of globalization has been sweeping across the nation changing its economic and social contours and challenging the established socioeconomic systems. With the impact of globalization being felt significantly in social, cultural and economic spheres of Sri Lanka, the university system has become no exception in dealing with its consequences. With the globalization, we have witnessed privately owned universities and institutions that offer higher education have been established in the country. Further, an increased number of foreign universities have established their operations in Sri Lanka to attract local student population.

However, the state university system needs to face the challenges posed by the globalization by acquiring the capability to effectively counter its negative impacts. This is vital for the university system as it is responsible for providing the knowledge and expertise services required for the nation's economic development. Failure to provide the aforesaid knowledge and expertise services will ultimately result in privately owned institutions and foreign universities stepping into fulfill the vacuum leading to a massive outflow of foreign exchange and jeopardizing the national interests.

In order to face the challenged posed by the globalization, the university system needs to ensure its long-term self sustainability and growth without the dependence on the state financing. The achievement of self sustainability and growth requires constant monitoring of the macroeconomic environment and identifying the threats and opportunities that exist in the environment. The university systems should be capable enough to guard against the threats that are looming and also capitalize on the opportunities for its economic benefits. It is in these opportunities in the macroeconomic environment that the university system would find avenues for long-term financial self sustainability and growth.

Accordingly, the university system should develop capabilities to constantly monitor the macroeconomic environment for opportunities and threats and at the same time devise strategies to offset the treats and capitalize on opportunities for its financial self sustainability and growth. Due to the fact that long term financial self sustainability and growth are related to the macroeconomic environment, they can be termed as the strategic objectives of the university system. Hence, the main objective of the state university system is to put in place strategies to ensure survival, long term financial self-sustainability and growth of the system (henceforth referred to as 'strategic objectives').

As part of the government's free education policy, the undergraduate programmes (leading to a first degree) conducted by the state university system has to be offered on non-income generating basis. Therefore, unlike the private sector institutions and foreign universities that offer undergraduate programmes, state university system cannot offer undergraduate programmes for income generating purposes. However, the Post Graduate programmes (programmes for which the entry qualification is a first degree or an equivalent qualification) such as Post Graduate diploma, masters and doctoral can be offered on a fee basis. The other services that can be offered by the universities and affiliated institutions on a fee basis include the specialized services such as consultancy, research and development, testing and certifying. Therefore, the state university system should thrive to use its Post Graduate programs and specialized services to ensure achievement of the strategic objectives.

The aim of this research is to examine the potency of the state university system to be effective in implementing strategies towards the achievement of strategic objectives and whether cultural paradigms that exist within state universities impact the achievement of the said objectives. The study is confined to investigate two universities in Sri Lanka where, one of them specialized in Technology and Technical education (University of Moratuwa) while the other is predominantly specialized in Management, Pure/Natural Sciences and Social Sciences (University of Kelaniya).

1.2 Identification of the problem

In order for the state university system to function as a vibrant forward looking and an effective knowledge creator and a disseminator, it has to grow and develop its internal capabilities. However, the financial resources by way of state financing are insufficient for the university system to achieve its full potential as an effective institution. Hence, the university system will require sourcing its own financial resources for its self sustainability and growth. The university system needs to become a vibrant income generating entity in order for it's to be financially self sustainable. The income generating opportunities are currently available in the macroeconomic environment in Sri Lanka as well as in the regional and global sphere. Globalization has brought about ample opportunities for higher education institutions such as the state economic system to offer its services and generate the much needed financial resources that are vital for its long-term financial self sustainability and growth. At the same time globalization has brought about sever competition to the macroeconomic environment of the country by way of higher educational institutions that compete for the student population of Sri Lankan which seeks postgraduate level qualification. Hence, in order to be competitive in the environment, the university

system needs to constantly monitor the environment for opportunities and devise strategies to capitalize on the said strengths.

However, it has been observed that the state university system so far has not been able to effectively identify the full potential in the macroeconomic environment that can be capitalized to generate much needed financial resources. The system has an array of advantages over the other privately owned higher education institutions that are competing in the marketplace. At the outset, the state higher education system is the repository of nation's knowledge and talent. The system has in its human capital, the best academic and professional skills that the nation has ever produced. It has all the necessary infrastructure scattered across the entire island. The Sri Lanka's higher education system has a reputation of being one of the best in South Asia and its degrees are recognized world over.

With all the above critical success factors in place, the state university system does not seem to have devised and implemented appropriate strategies to capitalize on the opportunities that are available in the macroeconomic environment. As such, it indicates that there is a problem that exists within the state university system that prevents it from monitoring the macroeconomic environment, identifying opportunities in the environment and devising strategies to capitalize on the identified opportunities to achieve strategic objectives of long term self sustainability and growth.

When shedding light on the above problem from different angles, one of the key observations that come to the forefront is the fact that the university system is highly people dependent. Any knowledge based organization has a greater degree of dependence on its human capital and the behavioral aspects of its knowledge workforce can have a greater impact on its success.

Similarly, the institution's capability to monitor the macroeconomic environment for opportunities and devise and implement strategies for capitalization of such opportunities need the high degree of involvement of the human capital of that organization. The university system broadly comprise of two functional segments of staff, i.e. academic and non academic. In order to achieve successful implementation of strategies, there is a range of attributes that must be present in human resources. These attributes will include the commitment, involvement, motivation and willingness to change. Research in this area clearly indicates that cultural paradigms that exist within the organization play a major role in determining the aforementioned attributes of the human resources.

The university system has been a state owned institution and as a result, has inculcated cultural paradigms and dynamics that are inherent in the state sector. In the contrary, the implementation of strategies to achieve strategic objectives will not be well facilitated in a culture with inappropriate cultural paradigms and dynamics that are inherent in the state sector institutions.

Hence the problem in this research is the impedance exerted on the efforts to achieve strategic objectives by the perceived existence of inappropriate cultural paradigms and dynamics in the state university system.

These inappropriate cultural paradigms and dynamics will lead to problems when it comes to implementation of strategies to achieve the strategic objectives of long term self sustainability of the university system.

1.3 Objectives of the study

Through this research, it is intend to investigate following.

1. To investigate the cultural paradigms of the academic and Administrative staff of the state university system of Sri Lanka with reference to Post Graduate Programmes of two state universities, i.e. University of Moratuwa and University of Kelaniya .
2. To investigate the level of effectiveness of PG (Post Graduate) programmes leading to survival, long term sustainability and growth of PG Programmes of the two Universites.
3. To compare cultural paradigms and effectiveness of PG programmes of the two universities.

To evaluate the Cultural Paradigms 100 survey questionnaires were distributed among the academic and administrative staff who involved in PG programmes of each University. Effectiveness of the PG programmes were also measured by using a questionnaire by means of structured interviews conducted with each department of the faculties.

Even though Sri Lanka has sixteen State Universities the scope of this research is limited to University of Moratuwa and University of Kelaniya. This research is a combination of empirical and theoretical nature as the concept was adopted from previous research done by Denison and Mishra (1995) and Kim Cameron (1978).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Organizational culture

Since organizations represent a cross section of the society, the organizations also display cultures that are unique to each organization. Organizational behaviourists have been making attempts to identify and define organizational cultures since very early stages of scientific management.

According to Aiman-Smith (2004), organizational culture is a commonly held in-the-mind framework of organizational members. This framework contains basic assumptions and values. These basic assumptions and values are taught to new members as the way to perceive, think, feel, behave, and expect others to behave in the organization. Towards identification of organizational culture, Schein (1999), made an attempt to define organizational culture in a more pragmatic way. Schein (1999) says that organizational culture is developed over time as people in the organization learn to deal successfully with problems of external adaptation and

internal integration. It becomes the common language and the common background. As such the culture arises out of what has been successful for the organization.

In an attempt to identify the culture from its qualitative aspect, Aiman-Smith (2004) puts forward a series of facets that can be observed within an organization. These facets or observations provide the observer a glimpse of the culture that is present in the organization. These facets can be described as Observations: What do offices look like? How are people dressed?, where do they eat lunch? How would you characterize the people in the hall – formal or informal? Laughing or serious? What kinds of pictures, signs and jokes are on walls? Listen for particular language.

2.2 Cultural paradigms

The cultural paradigms are clusters of basic assumptions into which they are grouped. These clusters are formed due to the human requirement of pattern and order. There are five basic cultural paradigms explained by Schein (1992). Different researchers have put forward various paradigms based on the research that they have conducted. According to Schein, there are four basic paradigms i.e. Organization's relationship to its environment, the nature of reality and truth, the nature of the human nature, the nature of human activity and the nature of human relationships. These cultural paradigms are highly fundamental in nature and critically examine the basic human psychological behaviours. As such applicability of these paradigms in empirical study of an educational institute is remote.

2.3 Organizational culture and effectiveness

The original framework for this study stems from the organizational culture model developed by Denison and his colleagues as a general framework (Denison, 1984, 1990, 1996; Denison & Mishra 1995, 1998; Denison & Neale, 1996; Denison & Young, 1999). This stream of research has made an important contribution by developing an explicit model of organizational culture and effectiveness and a valid method to measure organizational culture. Using this approach with top executives in 764 organizations, Denison and Mishra (1995) showed that the four different cultural traits were related to different criteria of effectiveness. For example, this research found that the stability traits of mission and consistency were the best predictors of profitability, the flexibility traits of involvement and adaptability were the best predictors of innovation, and the external orientation traits of adaptability and mission were the best predictors of sales growth. The Denison model is based on four cultural traits of effective organizations. These four traits are described as Involvement, Consistency, Adaptability, and Mission. A more complete review linking these traits to the literature has been provided by Denison and Mishra (1995).

2.4 Organizational effectiveness

Several models have been put forward for the study of organizational effectiveness. Each model has a unique emphasis. The effectiveness of organizations in achieving goals at the organizational level is called organizational effectiveness (Cameron and Whetten, 1983; Quinn and Rohrbaugh, 1983). The organizational effectiveness is also defined as the extent to which an organization fulfills the objectives (Thibodeaus and Favilla, 1995). The organizational effectiveness emphasized process control,

information management and goal setting (Quinn, 1998; Desion et al., 2004). Handna and Adas (1996) identified fourteen organizational effectiveness variables into the four general categories for analyzing the organizational characteristics. When Boerman and Bechger (1997) researched the decentralized decision making and organizational effectiveness, they adopted the growth of the organization, interaction with the field, evaluation by external factors, stability, control, the use of management information systems, commitment and educational planning items of organizational effectiveness.

2.5 Research on organizational effectiveness of higher education institutions

In the research paper titled ‘Organizational Effectiveness In Higher Education; Measures, Measurement And Evaluation’, Sevgül Karagöz states that the result of many researches shows high effectiveness from the individual point of view and in realization of an object for the lecturers, they may show low effectiveness at the sub units and bottom level of the organization (Cameron, 1978, Pg. 604). In Cameron’s (1981,Pg. 41) studies, the four basic fields of organizational effectiveness has been defined as academic, morale, adaptation to the external environment and fields outside program Fields as dimensions of effectiveness in higher educational institutions. These dimensions can be illustrated as follows in Table 1.

TABLE 1: BASIC FIELDS OF ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

Fields	Dimensions
External Adaptation Field	Professional development of students System’s clarity and environmental interaction
Field of Moral	Educational satisfaction of students Job satisfaction of lecturers Organizational health
Academic Field	Academic development of students Professional development of lecturers Ability to acquire source
Field Outside Program	Personal development of students

Source : 2008 EABR & TLC Conferences Proceedings

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Conceptual model

It is important to develop a conceptual model with the view of conceptualizing the research problem and clearly identifying the various aspects of the research objectives. The two most important aspects of the research objectives are the cultural paradigms that exists in the Universities and its impact on the effectiveness of postgraduate programs conducted by the universities.

FIGURE 1 : CONCEPTUAL MODEL

3.1.1 Independent Variable

The independent variable in this research is identified as the specific cultural paradigms that exist. The paradigm is expressed by way of four dimensions that are indicated in the model and they were measured by a standard questionnaire with changes to suit Sri Lanka. Past research conducted into this area clearly indicates that the culture is dynamic and it could be altered to achieve intended organizational objectives. Hence, cultural paradigms were treated as the independent variable. The independent variables were adopted from the models put forward Denison and Mishra (1995).

The key concept of Cultural Paradigm involved in the conceptual model depicted in Figure 1 can be further illustrated as follows :

Involvement

This involves the degree of empowerment of their staff, building the organization around teams and develop human capability at all levels. It further indicates the commitment to work and feel of belongingness of the organization. People at all levels feel that they have some input to decisions affecting their work. They also feel that the work is directly connected to the objectives of the organization.

Consistency

This is the display of high level of consistence, coordination and integration. Behavior is rooted in a set of core values, and leaders and followers are skilled at reaching agreement even when there are diverse points of view. This type of consistency is a powerful source of stability and internal integration that results from a common mindset and a high degree of conformity.

Adaptability

This is marked by adaptability to their customers, take risks and learn from their mistakes, and have capability and experience at creating change. They are continuously changing the system so that they are improving the organizations' collective abilities to provide value for their customers.

Mission

This is the basis for the organizations future and it contains basic direction along which the organization would progress. The mission primarily consists of the environmental opportunities and threats that it will perceive in the environment and its internal strategic intent to offset threats and capitalize opportunities.

3.1.2 Dependent Variable

The dependent variable in this research will be the effectiveness of the postgraduate programs of the two universities, which will be represented by four dimensions of effectiveness indicators that will represent the effectiveness parameters that are characteristic to higher educational institutions. It was measured by a separate questionnaire. The dependent variables were adopted from the models put forward by Cameron in 1981. Using this conceptual model it is intended to construct hypotheses that will measure the organizational effectiveness or the postgraduate programs conducted by the two universities.

The key concept of Organizational Effectiveness involved in the conceptual model depicted in Figure 1 can be further illustrated as follows :

Academic

This involves basic concepts such as academic-Academic Development of Students, Professional Development of Lecturers and ability to acquire resources.

Morale

This dimension encompasses concepts such as educational satisfaction of students, Job satisfaction of lecturers and Organizational Health.

Adaptation to the external environment

This dimension takes into account factors such as Professional Development of students, System's clarity and environmental interaction.

Field outside Program

This dimension basically deals with personal development of students.

3.2 Hypothesis of the study

Based on the above conceptual model in Figure 1, It is proposed to put forward the following hypotheses for this research.

- H1: There is a relationship between cultural paradigms and organizational effectiveness of Postgraduate programmes of the two universities

- H2: Technology oriented university has cultural paradigms that are more conducive for higher levels of organizational effectiveness

3.3 Sample of the study

Sample Selection to measure Culture was carried out using the stratified random sampling technique and a sample of 100 respondents from each university were selected. The strata consist of academic staff members ranging from the level of Professor to Probationary Lecturer and administrative staff members (Deputy Registrar/Deputy Bursar to Assistant Registrar/Assistant Bursar) who are actively involved in postgraduate programmes. The Faculties that are covered from each university is as follows:

University of Kelaniya (UOK)

All the Departments of the following faculties involved in PG studies

- Faculty of Social Science and Humanities
- Faculty of Science
 - Industrial Management
 - Microbiology
- Faculty of Management and Commerce
- Postgraduate Institute of Pali and Buddhist Studies (PGIPBS)
- Postgraduate Institute of Archaeology (PGIA)

University Of Moratuwa (UOM)

All the Departments of the following faculties involved in PG studies

- Faculty of Engineering
- Faculty of Architecture
- Faculty of Information Technology

The data related to effectiveness mostly recorded and maintained in the universities and institutions were collected from the respective institution or a representative appointed by the institution or department and finally rounded up to Faculty-wise figures of seven Faculties of the two Universities.

3.4 Data collection instrument

3.4.1 Questionnaire to Measure Culture

The core section of the questionnaire consists of questions to measure the organizational culture in the respective respondent's university. The questions in the core section of the questionnaire invite the respondents to answer on the likert scale of 1 to 5. The questions are based on Denison and Mishra's standard questionnaire published by Denison and Mishra (1995). This questionnaire was adapted to suite to the contest of two universities researched.

Each of the dimensions was measured using a questionnaire containing approximately 9 questions for each dimension. The responses were calculated based on a 5 point Likret Scale (5 = strongly agree, 1 = strongly disagree).

3.4.2 Questionnaire to Measure Effectiveness

A separate questionnaire was also used to elicit data in relation to the effectiveness aspect of the conceptual model. This questionnaire was adopted from Kim Cameron, who in 1986 published a paper based on his research titled A Study of Organizational Effectiveness and its Predictors. The research was conducted with special reference to the effectiveness of Universities and Colleges. The questionnaire was again adapted to suite to the scenario of the two universities. The questions contained in this questionnaire are open-ended and required specific responses from the respondent. This information was received by way of measurable and figures.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Cultural Dimensions in both the universities

As shown in Figure 2, the presence of the four main cultural dimensions was analysed with respect to both the universities as a whole. In this analysis it is clear that both universities has scored significantly well in Mission. This indicates that both these universities have considered seriously about the long term objectives.

On the other hand, both the universities have shown comparatively low levels of consistency. The main factors that have affected the consistency are the relative difficulty in reaching an agreement through consultation and consensus. Furthermore, the responses indicate that there is a difficulty among the staff members of different

postgraduate programs to share a common perspective. The results also indicate deficiencies in cross functional coordination.

FIGURE 2: THE PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT CULTURAL DIMENSIONS IN THE TWO UNIVERSITIES

4.2 Identification of the cultural paradigm with respect to each University

The main objectives of this research involve identification of the cultural paradigms that exists in the two universities under review. In the light of these objectives it is essential that the cultural dimensions of the two universities are identified and analysed separately. A clear understanding of the different cultural paradigm of the two universities and identification of these cultures with the respective effectiveness levels of the universities separately will lead help us to identify the most conducive culture that facilitates higher levels of effectiveness.

FIGURE3: UNIVERSITY- WISE ANALYSIS OF FOUR CULTURAL DIMENSIONS

As illustrated in Figure 3, when the Involvement dimension is considered, it is clear that the UOM (University of Moratuwa) has shown a higher score compared to UOK (University of Kelaniya). This indicates that the cultural traits such as team work, team efforts, sharing of information and the organization's ability to improve the skill levels of its employees are playing a major role. The high involvement on the other hand leads to higher levels of motivation in the part of the employees. This higher level of motivation helps the employees to achieve higher levels of effectiveness. Further, being technology oriented university, there is greater degree of interconnectivity among different functions of the university. For instance, different faculties of UOM have common areas where, it promotes greater team work among human capital of different faculties.

On the other hand UOK displays comparatively lesser degree of involvement. In the analysis of responses, it was clear that there was a low level of emphasis on team work in the UOK. Further, the responses clearly indicated that there are low levels of interaction between different faculties. The main reason for this is perceived to be the amount of interdependence between different faculties. For instance, Faculty of Science may not have anything common with the Faculty of Humanities. As such, the employees of different faculties show lack of capability to interact. This may be the main reason for the university's insignificant levels of information being not made widely available and shared among staff members. It has also been shown that majority of the employees do not believe in their ability to make an impact in the university. This can be attributed to the high levels of hierarchical control that has been displayed in its organizational structure. Hierarchical control levels fails to inculcate initiative in the workforce as the control usually tends to be authority oriented in nature.

In terms of consistency, the two universities do not show a major difference between each other. The mean score of the two universities is hovering around 3.5 to 3.3 indicating the comparatively low levels. This indicates that the employees of both these universities lack the positive behavioural traits such as the capability to consensus through dialog and negotiations, difficulty in reaching agreements on key issues, common perspective among staff and high degree of compartmentalization. Although these factors are present in both the universities, our data shows that employees of UOM show a comparatively higher levels of consistency related traits. For instance, it has been found that the staff members of the UOM are less confined to their own area of work. Most of the members are interacting with each other in conducting PG programs. This is clearly evidenced in the case of the PG program on Management of Technology where the faculty members of Engineering Disciplines participate in management related programs. Similarly there is a greater degree of sharing of knowledge and resources among different functions. It was also observed that the staff members are in a clear position to discuss matters with each other in a conducive environment with a view of reaching commonly agreed conclusions.

It has been observed that these cultural traits are rare among the employees of UOK. The respondents have clearly indicated that there is lack of interaction among different faculties in the university. This can be attributed to totally different areas of interest among the employees of different faculties and the different professional backgrounds that they come from. Furthermore, the responses indicate that it is rather

difficult for them to reach conclusions through dialog and negotiations. Negative cultural traits such as high compartmentalization, lack of team playing, lack of consensus on critical issues leads to inability to bring about the much required levels of effectiveness of the university.

Adaptability is one of the most important cultural dimensions in an organization. Highly adaptable organizations have the capability to respond well to the environmental changes and are capable of evading threats in the environment and capitalise on opportunities. When the two universities are considered, there are evidences that the adaptability related cultural trait are present in moderate degrees in both the universities. However, employees of UOM have shown considerably high adaptability traits compared to the employees of the UOK.

It has been observed that the employees of UOM have displayed high levels of disposition in their ability to respond to environmental factors and change accordingly, ability to respond well to competitors and environment, embark on continuous adaptation and improvement. Further, these employees believe that failures provide opportunities for them to learn and improve so that they are well positioned to face the environmental challenges. For an organization to be strategically successful, the organization will have to eternally look for environmental opportunities. It is in the external environment that enormous opportunities are available. At the same time, factors such as competition and other macroeconomic and social factors in the environment could also threaten the organizational existence and growth. During the interview with the employees of the UOM it was revealed that the employees are well aware of the macroeconomic environmental factors. A good example for this is the high level of interest of the students in the Postgraduate Program on Management of Technology. Having identified the rapid growth in the information technology sector and also the potential of the IT professionals to assume higher managerial roles in the IT driven organizations, the university commenced this program. The enormous response to this program clearly identifies the university's capability to scan the environment for opportunities and capitalize on those for organizational growth. Furthermore, the university has shown an enormous potential in changing internally. This is evidenced by the wide array of specialized services that the university provides in fee generating basis. The internal organizational structure has undergone adaptations to be able to effectively deliver these specialized services through its own staff members generating an income for the university.

On the other hand, UOK has not displayed a high capability to identify and respond to the environmental factors. The questionnaire responses show that the university is still continuing with the traditional PG programs such without gearing themselves to embark on programs that have a wide demand from the target market. For instance, there is a wide demand for management disciplines such as Human Resources, Banking and Finance, Consumer Behaviour and Marketing, Financial Management, etc. However, apart from the Faculty of Science, the other faculties have not designed postgraduate programs to address the needs of the student population. This lack of adaptability will lead to the competition making advantage of the opportunities available in the environment and posing a threat to the university.

Mission is the most vital component in any organization that determines the future of that organization. The mission is based on the long term vision of the organization which provides a clear picture to the employees of all levels with respect to the destination of the organization in the future. The mission is also the foundation stone for setting of organizational objectives that are milestones in the organization's path towards realizing the final vision. The main features of the mission statement include its clarity. The mission cannot be ambiguous leading to confusion among the employees as to the direction that they are heading. The mission should also provide a greater degree of motivation for the employees to lead them along the path towards achievement of ultimate organizational objectives.

When the UOM is considered, its mission related cultural dimension is far superior compared to the UOK. It has been discovered in the responses to questionnaire that the UOM has a long-term purpose and direction. It has a futuristic vision that states "To be the institution of academic excellence in Sri Lanka for technological disciplines with national relevance and international recognition". The long term purpose and direction is clearly indicated in this statement and the university has been able to rally the employees towards the common purpose. The employees have clearly indicated that the clear mission provides meaning and direction to the organization. This factor is very important in achieving effectiveness as the employees are very clear as to what the organization is expecting of them. For instance, one of the objectives of the university is to achieve international recognition. It has been well evidenced in our interviews that the employees of the university clearly identify objective and are working towards achieving the same. It has also been observed that the staff members are motivated towards achieving these objectives. Furthermore, based on the vision of the organization, the UOM has put in place a range of strategies to reach its ultimate future objectives. Our research reveals that the employees are well aware of the objectives and are working towards achieving the same. The most important factor in the mission component of the culture is the ability of the workforce to rally around the common vision. It has been clear from the interview responses that the vision has been developed with wider participation of various levels of staff members and therefore, the staff members have an ownership to the vision. As a result the employees are highly motivated to working towards achieving this mission.

When the UOK is considered it has scored low compared to the UOM in the mission related cultural dimension. The university's direction is spelt in its vision "The vision of the University of Kelaniya is to be one of the leading universities in Asia, which will prepare internationally competitive graduates, promote values of sustainable society and conduct outstanding research to improve quality of life". Our research clearly indicates that the staff members are aware of the presence of a vision and a mission for the university. However, the employees have indicated that the goals and the objectives emanating from the vision are ambiguous. There can be many reasons for the employees to feel that the goals are ambiguous. One of them may be the goals are not well communicated to the employees so that they are not very clear as to what is expected of them. Another aspect of the ambiguous goals can be differences in opinion of the top management that set these goals. Their difference of opinion carves into the goals making them less clear and more difficult to comprehend. The risk of ambiguous goals is that they can lead to severe failure in achievement of effectiveness targets as the employees are not clear of their final achievement. Another negative aspect of the mission dimension in relation to the UOK lies in the mission's ability to

bring about the much needed motivation of the employees. Modern managerial science clearly identifies that the vision itself should create a high level of motivation for the employees. This will help the organization to place low emphasis on other motivational incentives such as pay, fringe benefits, etc. In view of the above our finding that the UOK lags behind in its mission related cultural dimension is clearly demonstrated.

4.3 Analysis of cultural dimensions with respect to Faculty

In the analysis of cultural dimension in respect of the two universities, it has been observed that UOM has relatively more conducive cultural traits compared to the UOK. In terms of the mean score for the four cultural dimensions, there is a significant difference in the mean score of UOM (mean = 3.82) and the UOK (mean = 3.36). However, a more in-depth analysis has been carried out in to the level of faculties of each university. This was possible due to the method of data analysis where interview responses obtained from each faculty was analysed for the presence of cultural trails with respect to each cultural dimension i.e. involvement, consistency, adaptability and mission.

As shown in Figure 4, in this analysis, it has been considered the three faculties of the UOM separately and an attempt has been made to identify the presence of the four cultural dimensions in these three faculties. Our observation indicates that that Faculty of Information Technology has scored the highest mean score for in respect of all four dimensions followed by the Faculty of architecture and the Faculty of Engineering.

If the Faculty of Information Technology is considered, it has shown a significant presence of the mission related cultural traits. This level is the highest level among any of the faculties even if both the universities are considered. The Faculty to have a very high mission related culture is essential due to the sector related macroeconomic contours that prevail in the local and global arena of information technology. The sector is fast evolving with the advancements based on innovation. This has necessitated various stakeholders in the IT sector to be more forward-looking in terms of the environment that they operate. The faculty has also shown a high degree of involvement, consistency and adaptability. The cultural traits related to these dimensions are also important provided the dynamics of the industry.

The Faculty of Architecture has indicated higher levels of traits in relation to both involvement and mission. Architecture is an area based on more creativity and innovation. In order to promote a culture of creativity, innovation and free thinking, it is essential that there is a culture of less hierarchical control, more teamwork and greater degree of sharing of each other's knowledge across the organization. As such the faculty is benefiting from its high involvement oriented cultural traits. Similarly, the faculty has a higher degree of mission related cultural traits. In this aspect, the field of architecture is evolving with architects around the world is becoming more innovative in their designing and knowledge. A clear vision and a related mission are very helpful for the faculty to be more focused in its long term objectives in such environments.

When the Faculty of Engineering is considered, it has indicated relatively higher levels of mission and involvement related cultural traits while it is lowest among the

three faculties for consistency related cultural traits. If we consider some of the cultural traits that has have been measured to identify the presence of consistency, they involve factors such as common perspective among the staff members in relation to major decisions, the ability to reach common conclusions on critical issues, ability to reach reconciliation when a range of diverse views exist, to work on common set of ethical values. These factors are of utmost importance for a university to be highly effective. These cultural traits determine the faculty’s capability to respond to environment factors quickly and accurately leading to capitalization of these factors to achieve organizational objectives. An organization failing to reach common agreement within its internal setup or showing high degree of compartmentalization will lag behind its competitors in the dynamic macroeconomic environment.

FIGURE 4 : FACULTY- WISE ANALYSIS OF FOUR CULTURAL DIMENSIONS

The five faculties and the two PG institutes of the UOK are considered, there is a significant difference in the mean score with respect to four cultural dimensions in comparison to the mean score the three faculties of the UOM. In order to identify the level presence of the four cultural dimensions within each faculty, we will compare the faculty-wise mean score for the cultural dimensions.

In terms of mean score for the four cultural dimensions, the PGIPBS (Post Graduate Institute of Pali and Buddhist Studies) and the Faculty of Humanities show a higher degree of presence of all four cultural dimensions. The consistency and mission related cultural dimensions are far superior in the PGIPBS compared to the other faculties and institutions of UOK. The consistency is an important factor that encompasses cultural traits such as common consensus on key issues, low compartmentalization, ability to reach an agreement on key issue and alignment of all employees towards a common goal. Further, the institute appears to have a greater degree of mission related cultural traits such as clear and vision, unambiguous goals and long term orientation. However, the institute seems lacking in adaptability dimension. This is a very important cultural dimension which encompasses traits such as the tendency to carry out internal changes to suite to the requirements of the

students, calculated risk taking, ability to respond well to the changes in the environmental and competitors.

PGIPBS is an institute that mainly caters to Buddhist higher education. The program is known to have attracted a large number of foreign students as well as students of other professional disciplines. Our findings reveal that there is a growing demand for the program from members of the society holding important positions in the healthcare sector, banking and financial services sectors and armed forces are showing keen interest in this program. As such this is a program with greater growth potential for the UOK. However, its lacking of adaptability related cultural traits despite having high degree of mission related cultural traits will lead to low effectiveness levels.

The Faculty of Humanities has displayed a greater degree of presence of involvement related cultural traits. This indicates that the faculty works with greater emphasis on team building and team efforts, continuous skill development of employees and horizontal control structures. These are traits contribute well for effectiveness enhancement as they lead directly to greater degree of internal dynamism and efficiency.

When the other faculties of the UOK are considered they do not indicate as displaying a significant presence of the important cultural dimensions. Although most of the faculties have indicated the presence of mission related cultural traits, the lack of other cultural trails offset the positive impact of the mission dimension in their attempt to achieve greater degree of effectiveness.

4.4 Effectiveness of the Universities

Analysis of efectiveness by considering both the universities as a whole

In the effectiveness analysis, the Engineering and Architecture faculties can be placed on 1st and 2nd positions on a rank of 1 to 9 while the Faculty of information technology can be placed in the third position. This clearly indicates that two out of the three faculties of the UOM can be included with in the 1st quartile in the rank order indicating high levels of effectiveness, while the Faculty of information technology placing at the 4th position on the ranking order of 1 to 9. Hence it is clear that all three faculties of the UOM show high degree of effectiveness out of the faculties of the two universities under investigation.

An analysis was carried out to identify the specific effectiveness parameters where the three faculties of UOM have performed well. In the analysis it was discovered that the faculty of Engineering has shown the best performance in terms of

- (a) Total number of permanent faculty members on policy-making boards or committees
- (b) Number of faculty members earning a degree or charter after being hired
- (c) The amount of funds allocated for professional development of academic and administrative staff
- (d) Number of faculty with Doctorates
- (e) Number of continuous Education courses
- (f) Total Amount of revenue earned by conducting PG courses

Similarly, it has been noticed that the other two faculties of the UOM have been placed at higher ranks in term of effectiveness, making UOM the comparatively more effective university out of the two universities under investigation.

4.5 Relationship between Cultural Dimensions and Effectiveness

In the analysis, an attempt has been made to identify the university that is more effective out of the two universities under review and then analyse the relative presence of various cultural dimensions in the said university where the effectiveness has been found greater. This will lead the way to discover the relative presence of cultural dimensions in each of the faculties where the effectiveness ranking is high. This analysis will lead to conclusion of identifying the best cultural paradigm that will support best effectiveness levels.

It is clear that if the organization has a greater degree of mission related cultural traits with moderate levels of involvement and adaptability, the organization will be geared to adopt higher levels of effectiveness. It has also been found in the data analysis that the consistency related cultural dimensions are not significant determinants of the effectiveness as much as the mission involvement and adaptability related cultural traits.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The data with regard to the both universities were analyzed in conjunction, it was revealed that the both universities displayed a high degree of mission related cultural traits. In addition, involvement and adaptability were present in moderation. However, a more in-depth analysis to the two universities, the salient features in relation to each cultural dimension was surfacing.

In the case of UOM, all three faculties studied displayed a very high degree of mission related cultural dimensions (mean 4.16). In other words, UOM is equipped with a well designed forward-looking vision and related mission statement which was clear all employees foe of the organization. Furthermore, the employees were motivated to be guided by their vision towards the future leading to achievement of organizational objectives. Further, all three faculties of UOM had a comparatively higher degree of involvement (mean 3.86) and also a greater degree of adaptability (mean 3.69) was displayed.

On the other hand, UOK does not have very strong mission related cultural traits (mean 3.38) compared to UOM. This is well evidenced by the difference in mean score of mission dimensions of the two universities. Further, UOK shows very low degree of consistency (mean 3.27), while displaying adaptability (mean 3.29) and involvement (mean 3.47) cultural traits in moderation.

In the analysis of effectiveness data, a rank scale was used as the type of information gathered to evaluate effectiveness which could not be measured on Likert scale. The information included aspects such as financial performance, student satisfaction, student related parameter, etc. This information was quantified and then each faculty of the respective universities were ranked according to 9 such effectiveness related quantifiables.

In the analysis it was clear that two out of three faculties of the UOM are ranked 1st and 2nd while the third faculty was ranked 4th. The faculty of Information Technology was ranked 4 due to it being a newly established faculty and majority of the quantifiable that were investigated were disadvantageous for new faculties. As such it is clear that UOM is far greater in terms of effectiveness. On the other hand, all faculties of UOK were well behind the quantifiable parameters of effectiveness.

Out of the two universities evaluated, UOM is a technology oriented institution while UOK is a non-technical oriented institution. In our analysis of information it was clear that UOM has displayed far superior effectiveness levels. Out of the three faculties of UOM, two faculties occupy first two slots of the ranked effectiveness scales. As such it could be concluded that technology oriented universities have a greater degree of effectiveness. Based on our hypothesis that cultural paradigms play a significant role in influencing effectiveness levels, it is clear that the cultural paradigm that exists in technology oriented university is more conducive to generate higher levels of effectiveness in its PG programs.

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